

The logo for PhenolQuest is a light green speech bubble containing the text "PhenolQuest" in a dark grey, sans-serif font. The background of the top half of the page features a repeating pattern of various fruits and vegetables, including carrots, apples, pears, and leafy greens, rendered in a light green line-art style. A white wavy line separates this patterned area from the white background below.

PhenolQuest

Questionnaire on your dietary
intake of polyphenols

Polyphenols are naturally occurring compounds found in plant-based foods. Major sources of polyphenols include **fruits, dark chocolate, tea, coffee, and red wine.**

Several scientific studies have demonstrated the **health benefits of polyphenols**, particularly in preventing cardiovascular diseases and maintaining the balance of our gut microbiota.

This questionnaire has been **developed by a research team from the French National Institute for Agricultural Research, Food and Environment (INRAE)** to assess polyphenol consumption as accurately as possible in the context of scientific studies.

The questions you will answer aim to evaluate **your usual polyphenol intake based on your consumption, over the past year, of a selection of foods known for their richness in certain polyphenols.**

Please note that some foods you may frequently consume do not appear in the questionnaire for several reasons: either they contain little or no polyphenols, (e.g. zucchini), or the currently available data on their polyphenol content are still insufficient (e.g. melon).

Instructions

You will be guided step by step throughout the questionnaire to help you complete it accurately. Pay close attention to the explanations in each section.

Please note: Portion sizes can vary from one person to another. For each food item, a "reference portion" is provided, either as an illustrated portion ($\frac{1}{2}$ plate, 1 tablespoon, 1 fruit, etc.) and/or as a volume or weight (for example, 25 cl of a beverage or 50 g of a food). You will indicate how often, on average, you consumed the specified reference portion for each food item over the past 12 months.

Important: If your usual portion size differs from the reference portion, you will need to adjust your response. Here's how:

Example: The reference portion for green beans is $\frac{1}{2}$ plate

Situation 1: You consume green beans only during the summer. During this period, you eat them at about 4 times a week, with a quarter of plate per serving, for example in salads. Consuming 4 times per week at half the reference portion is equivalent to consuming the full reference portion 2 times per week. In this case, for green beans, you should select: "3 months per year" and then "2-3 times per week".

Situation 2: You eat a full plate of green beans (twice the size of the reference portion) at lunch, 2-3 times a week throughout the year. In this case, first indicate "12 months" and then "4 to 6 times a week" to account for the larger portion size.

Before filling out the questionnaire, please provide the following information :

Date of completion: ___ / ___ / ____

1. VEGETABLES, POTATOES and LEGUMES

Please indicate in the table below how many servings of each type of vegetable, (fresh, frozen, canned, raw, or cooked) you consumed on average per day, over the past year:

Note: Reference portion for vegetables = ½ plate

For each vegetable, please indicate:

On the first line, the number of months per year you consumed this vegetable,

On the second line, your consumption frequency during that period, adjusted if necessary according to the indicated reference portion.

If you never consume a particular vegetable, simply tick the "never" box and move on to the next vegetable.

FOOD (portion)	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS												
	never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
VEGETABLES (fresh or frozen, raw, cooked, or canned)													
Potatoes (except chips and crisps) (½ plate)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Salad (lettuce, lamb's lettuce, etc.) (½ plate)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Bell Pepper (½ bell pepper)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Which type(s) of bell pepper(s) have you consumed most often?													
<input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Green <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> All													
Cooked Spinach (½ plate)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Cherry tomatoes (10 cherry tomatoes)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Aubergine (½ plate)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													

	never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
Beetroot <i>(½ plate)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Broccoli <i>(½ plate)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Brussels Sprouts <i>(½ plate)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Green Cabbage <i>(½ plate)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Red Cabbage <i>(½ plate)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Kale <i>(½ plate)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Plantains <i>(½ plate)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Green Beans <i>(½ plate)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Artichoke <i>(1 artichoke or 3 hearts)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Celeriac <i>(½ plate, raw or cooked)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													

	never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
Onions ($\frac{1}{2}$ onion)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>

Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

Which type(s) of onion(s) have you consumed most often?

Red
 White/Spring
 Yellow
 All

LEGUMES

Kidney beans or black beans ($\frac{1}{2}$ plate)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

Broad Beans ($\frac{1}{2}$ plate)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

Pinto Beans ($\frac{1}{2}$ plate)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

White Beans ($\frac{1}{2}$ plate)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

Lentils ($\frac{1}{2}$ plate)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

Which type(s) of lentils have you consumed most often?

Red
 Green/blond
 Brown/du Puy/black
 All

SOUP

Vegetable Soup (1 soup plate/bowl)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

Soup with Legumes (1 soup plate/bowl)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

Onion soup (1 soup plate/bowl)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

Gazpacho / Tomato Soup (1 soup plate/bowl)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Once a month
 2 to 4 times a month
 2 to 3 times a week
 4 to 6 times a week
 Once a day
 2 to 3 times a day

2. FRESH, FROZEN, or COOKED FRUITS

Over the past year, and for each indicated seasons, how many servings of **frozen, fresh, or cooked fruits (excluding canned fruits, compotes, fruit purees and jams)** have you consumed on average per day?

One serving of fruit = one whole fruit (e.g. an apple), a handful of berries, ...

FRUITS	NUMBER OF FRUIT SERVINGS PER DAY											
	0	<1	1	1,5	2	2,5	3	3,5	4	5	6	7 or more
SPRING/SUMMER	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUTUMN/WINTER	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.1. Please indicate in the table below how many servings of **each type of fruits** (fresh, frozen, canned, raw, or cooked) **you consumed on average per day, over the past year.**

For each fruit, please indicate:

On the first line, the number of months per year you consumed this fruit,

On the second line, your consumption frequency during period, adjusted if necessary according to the indicated reference portion.

If you never consume a particular fruit, simply tick the "never" box and move on to the next fruit.

FOOD (portion)	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS												
	never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
FRUITS (fresh, frozen, or cooked)													
Apple (1 apple)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Which type(s) of apples have you consumed most often? <input type="checkbox"/> Table apples (Gala, Pink lady, Golden, ...) <input type="checkbox"/> Heritage apples (Canada, Boskoop ...) <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know													
Did you eat apples with the peel? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes													
Banana (1 banana)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													

	never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months		
Orange <i>(1 orange)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
Clementine or Mandarin <i>(1 fruit)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
Grapefruit <i>(½ grapefruit)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
Pear <i>(1 pear)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
Plums <i>(2 large or 4 small fresh plums)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
Apricot <i>(1 large apricot or 2 small ones)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
Peach or Nectarine <i>(1 fruit)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
<i>Did you eat peach or nectarine with the peel?</i>				<input type="checkbox"/> Yes				<input type="checkbox"/> No				<input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes			
Grape <i>(≈ 1 handful or 15-20 grapes)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
<i>Type(s) of grape consumed most regularly?</i>				<input type="checkbox"/> Red				<input type="checkbox"/> White				<input type="checkbox"/> Both			
Persimmon <i>(1 persimmon)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
Kiwi <i>(1 kiwi)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					
Mango <i>(½ mango)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>		
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day					

	never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
Fig <i>(1 large fig or 2 small ones)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day		
Strawberries <i>(≈ 1 handful or 4/6 strawberries)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day		
Cherries <i>(1 handful or 10-12 cherries)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day		
Raspberries <i>(≈ 1 handful or 10-12 raspberries)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day		
Blackberries <i>(≈ 1 handful or 10-12 blackberries)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day		
Blueberries/ Bilberries <i>(≈ 1 handful)</i>	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
	<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day		

2.2. Have you consumed other fruits more than twice a week?

- No (Please proceed directly to question 3)
- Yes (Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below)

Fruit	Number of servings consumed per week

3. PROCESSED FRUITS

3.1. Canned fruits

Over the past year, have you consumed canned fruits at least once a month?

Note: If you consumed canned fruits once a week during the three winter months, this corresponds to 12 occasions of consumption over the year, equivalent to once a month.

- No (Please proceed directly to question 3.2)
- Yes (Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below. Note: This time, we ask you to average your consumption over the year)

Note: Reference portion = small ramekin or yogurt-sized cup (approximately 100g)

FOOD (portion)	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS						
	Never or <once a month	Once a month	2 to 4 times a month	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	2 to 3 times a day
Peach (1/2 cup)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pear (1/2 cup)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cherries (1/2 cup)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fruit Cocktail (1/2 cup)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Apricot (1/2 cup)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.2. Fruit compote or puree

Over the past year, have you consumed **fruit puree or compote** at least once a month?

Note: If you consumed compote once a week during the 3 winter months, this corresponds to 12 occasions of consumption over the year, equivalent to once a month

- No (Please proceed directly to question 3.3)
- Yes (Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below. Note: This time, we ask you to average your consumption over the year)

Note: Reference portion = small ramekin or yogurt-sized cup (approximately 100g)

FOOD (portion)	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS												
	Never or <once a month	Once a month	2 to 4 times a month	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	2 to 3 times a day						
Apple compote (1/2 cup)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Compote apple with another fruit (1/2 cup)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Select 1 to 3 fruits most often present in your compote in addition to apple		<input type="checkbox"/> Apricot	<input type="checkbox"/> Banana	<input type="checkbox"/> Chestnut	<input type="checkbox"/> Quince	<input type="checkbox"/> Strawberry	<input type="checkbox"/> Raspberry	<input type="checkbox"/> Mango	<input type="checkbox"/> Blueberry	<input type="checkbox"/> Peach (or nectarine)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pear	<input type="checkbox"/> Plums	<input type="checkbox"/> Others
Fruit puree (1/2 cup)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Select 1 to 3 fruits most often present in your fruit puree		<input type="checkbox"/> Peach	<input type="checkbox"/> Apricot	<input type="checkbox"/> Pear	<input type="checkbox"/> Cherries	<input type="checkbox"/> Strawberry	<input type="checkbox"/> Raspberry	<input type="checkbox"/> Mango	<input type="checkbox"/> Others				
Chestnut cream (2 tablespoons)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						

3.3. Fruit jam and jelly

Over the past year, have you consumed fruit **jam or jelly** at least once a month?

Note: If you consumed 1 serving (2 teaspoons) of jam once a week during 3 months, this corresponds to 12 occasions of consumption over the year, equivalent to once a month.

No (Please proceed directly to question 4)

Yes (Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below. Note: This time, we ask you to average your consumption over the year)

Note: Reference portion = 2 teaspoons

FOOD (portion)	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS						
	Never or <once a month	Once a month	2 to 4 times a month	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	2 to 3 times a day
Jam, jelly (2 teaspoons)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Select 1 to 3 type(s) of jam or jelly that you consumed most often.		<input type="checkbox"/> Raspberry	<input type="checkbox"/> Strawberry	<input type="checkbox"/> Blueberry	<input type="checkbox"/> Blackberry	<input type="checkbox"/> Blackcurrant	<input type="checkbox"/> Redcurrant
		<input type="checkbox"/> Apricot	<input type="checkbox"/> Orange	<input type="checkbox"/> Plums	<input type="checkbox"/> Figs	<input type="checkbox"/> Rhubarb	<input type="checkbox"/> Others

4. DRIED FRUITS & NUTS

Over the past year, have you consumed **nuts** (walnuts, almonds, hazelnuts, etc.) and/or **dried fruits** at least once a month?

- No (Please proceed directly to question 5)
- Yes (Please describe your consumption by filling out the tables below)

Note: Reference portion for nuts or dried fruits = one handful (approximately 30g)

Note: When filling out the table below please pay special attention to avoid counting the same consumption more than once.

First, complete your consumption of each type of dried fruit alone (i.e. not mixed with nuts), then, indicate your consumption of nuts alone or in a mix of nuts (e.g., walnuts and hazelnuts), finally, indicate your consumption of mixed dried fruits and nuts.

FOOD <i>(portion)</i>	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS						
	Never or <once a month	Once a month	2 to 4 times a month	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	2 to 3 times a day
DRIED FRUITS							
Dried Cranberries <i>(1 handful)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Prunes <i>(4 prunes)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dried Apricots <i>(4 dried apricots)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dried Figs <i>(2 dried figs)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dried Date <i>(4 dried dates)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Raisins <i>(1 handful)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
NUTS (alone or mixed)							
Nuts <i>(alone or mixed nuts) (1 handful)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Select 1 to 4 type(s) of nuts that you consumed most often</i>				<input type="checkbox"/> Almonds <input type="checkbox"/> Peanuts <input type="checkbox"/> Hazelnuts <input type="checkbox"/> Walnuts		<input type="checkbox"/> Pecans <input type="checkbox"/> Cashews <input type="checkbox"/> Pistachios	
MIXED DRIED FRUITS AND NUTS							
Mixed dried fruits and nuts <i>(1 handful)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Select 1 to 3 type(s) of nuts and 1 to 3 type(s) of dried fruits most often present in your mixes</i>				<u>Dried fruits:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Dried Apricots <input type="checkbox"/> Dried Figs <input type="checkbox"/> Dried Cranberries <input type="checkbox"/> Raisins		<u>Nuts :</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Almonds <input type="checkbox"/> Peanuts <input type="checkbox"/> Hazelnuts <input type="checkbox"/> Walnuts <input type="checkbox"/> Pecans <input type="checkbox"/> Cashews <input type="checkbox"/> Pistachios	

5. COCOA PRODUCTS

Over the past year, have you consumed **chocolate or chocolate desserts** (excluding beverages) at least once a month?

- No *(Please proceed directly to question 6)*
- Yes *(Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below, considering the specified portions)*

FOOD (portion)	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS							
	Never or <once a month	Once a month	2 to 4 times a month	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	2 to 3 times a day	4 times a day or more
Dark chocolate <i>(2 squares of a chocolate bar or 2 confectionery chocolates)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dark chocolate mousse <i>(1 ramekin or yogurt-sized cup)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dark chocolate cake/brownie <i>(1 slice of cake, or 1/8th of a cake)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Milk chocolate <i>(2 squares of a chocolate bar or 2 confectionery chocolates)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If you are feeling fatigued at this point in the questionnaire, we recommend taking a 15 minute break before continuing.

6. NON-ALCOHOLIC COLD BEVERAGES

6.1. Over the past year, have you consumed fruit juice at least once per month on average ?

Note: If you consumed 1 glass of fruit juice once a week during the 3 summer months, this corresponds to 12 occasions of consumption over the year, which is equivalent to once a month.

- No *(Please proceed directly to question 6.2)*
- Yes *(Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below)*

When you consumed fruit juice, what was your typical serving size?

15 cl

25 cl

For each beverage, please indicate in the table below:

On the first line, the number of months per year you consume this beverage,

On the second line, your frequency of consumption during that period

If you never consume a particular beverage, simply tick the "never" box and move on to the next beverage.

BEVERAGE	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS												
	never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
FRUIT JUICE													
Apple juice	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
<i>Which type of apple juice have you consumed most often</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial/clear <input type="checkbox"/> Artisan/cloudy <input type="checkbox"/> Both <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know													
Orange juice	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
<i>Which type(s) of orange juice have you consumed most often</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Freshly squeezed or 100% pure juice (store-bought) <input type="checkbox"/> All <input type="checkbox"/> Orange juice from concentrate <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know													
Citrus fruit juice	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Grapefruit juice	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Lemonade	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Grape juice	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Pomegranate juice	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													

	never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
Other fruit juice	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day			
Select 1 to 3 type(s) of other juices or nectars that you consumed most often		<input type="checkbox"/> Multifruit juice		<input type="checkbox"/> Cranberry juice				<input type="checkbox"/> Other(s):					
		<input type="checkbox"/> ACE juice		<input type="checkbox"/> Strawberry juice				1.					
		<input type="checkbox"/> Apricot juice		<input type="checkbox"/> Red fruits juice				2.					
		<input type="checkbox"/> Pear juice											
Smoothies	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day			
Select 1 to 3 fruit(s) most often used in your smoothies		<input type="checkbox"/> Red fruits		<input type="checkbox"/> Mango				<input type="checkbox"/> Other(s):					
		<input type="checkbox"/> Banana		<input type="checkbox"/> Orange				1.					
		<input type="checkbox"/> Strawberry		<input type="checkbox"/> Apple				2.					
		<input type="checkbox"/> Kiwi		<input type="checkbox"/> Pear									

6.2. Over the past year, have you consumed homemade iced tea or iced coffee, at least once a month?

- No (Please proceed directly to question 7)
- Yes (Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below)

For each beverage, please indicate:

On the first line, the number of months per year you consumed this beverage,
 On the second line, your frequency of consumption during that period
 If you never consume a particular beverage, simply tick the "never" box and move on to the next beverage.

BEVERAGE	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS												
	never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
Homemade Iced Tea	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day			
When you consumed homemade iced tea, what was your typical serving size?		<input type="checkbox"/> 15 cl											
Iced Coffee	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month		<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week		<input type="checkbox"/> Once a day	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day			
When you consumed Iced coffee, what was your typical serving size?		<input type="checkbox"/> 15 cl											

7. NON-ALCOHOLIC HOT BEVERAGES

7.1. During the past year, have you consumed coffee (or similar beverages like cappuccino, latte, etc) at least once a month?

- No (Please proceed directly to question 7.2)
 Yes (Please describe your consumption by completing the table below)

Note: Please pay attention when recording your consumption, particularly if you used different types of containers (cup, bowl, etc.). Refer to the table of correspondences provided below to calculate the correct number of servings.

BEVERAGE (serving size)	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS									
	Never	1 to 3 times a month	Once a week	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	Twice a day	3 times a day	4 times a day	5 times or more a day
COFFEE (capsule, filter, percolator, instant, ...)										
Espresso (1 espresso cup, 7cl)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Decaffeinated espresso (1 espresso cup, 7cl)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regular Long Coffee	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>When you consumed a long coffee, what was your typical serving size?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Standard cup (10cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Bowl (30cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Large cup or mug (25cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Varies (e.g., a bowl at breakfast, a cup at lunch)</p>										
<p>If you have ticked "Varies", please estimate the number of servings that you consumed on a typical day, using the explanations below.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 4,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 7 <input type="checkbox"/> 3,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 5,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 7,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 6 <input type="checkbox"/> 8 and more</p>										
<p>Correspondance :</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> A large Cup or A mug = 2,5 servings (25cl) </div> </div>										
<p>Example: 1 bowl of coffee in the morning, 1 large cup at noon, and 1 standard cup in the afternoon= 3 + 2,5 + 1 = 6,5 servings per day</p>										
<p>How did you drink your long coffee?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Light <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> Strong <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know</p>										

	Never	1 to 3 times a month	Once a week	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	Twice a day	3 times a day	4 times a day	5 times or more a day					
Decaffeinated Long Coffee	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
When you consumed a decaffeinated long coffee, what was your typical serving size?		<input type="checkbox"/> Standard cup (10cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Large cup or mug (25cl)			<input type="checkbox"/> Bowl (30cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Varies (e.g., a bowl at breakfast, a cup at lunch)										
If you have ticked "Varies", please estimate the number of servings that you consumed on a typical day, using the explanations above.				<input type="checkbox"/> 2,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 3,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 4,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 5,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 6,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 7,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 8 and more
How do you usually drink your decaffeinated long coffee?		<input type="checkbox"/> Light		<input type="checkbox"/> Medium		<input type="checkbox"/> Strong		<input type="checkbox"/> Don't know							
	Never	1 to 3 times a month	Once a week	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	Twice a day	3 times a day	4 times a day	5 times or more a day					
Coffee with milk or Latte or Cappuccino	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
When you consumed a Coffee with milk or Latte or Cappuccino, what was your typical serving size?		<input type="checkbox"/> Standard cup (10cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Large cup or mug (25cl)			<input type="checkbox"/> Bowl (30cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Varies (e.g., a bowl at breakfast, a cup at lunch)										
If you have ticked "Varies", please estimate the number of servings you consumed on a typical day, using the explanations above.				<input type="checkbox"/> 2,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 3,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 4,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 5,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 6,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 7,5	<input type="checkbox"/> 8 and more

7.2. During the past year, have you consumed **tea (excluding iced tea)** at least once a month?

- No (Please proceed directly to question 7.3)
- Yes (Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below)

Note: Please pay attention when recording your consumption, particularly if you use different types of containers (cup, bowl, etc.). Refer to the table of correspondences provided below to calculate the correct number of servings.

BEVERAGE	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS											
	Never	1 to 3 times a month	Once a week	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	Twice a day	3 times a day	4 times a day	5 times a day or more		
Black Tea	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
When you drank black tea, what was your typical serving size?		<input type="checkbox"/> Standard cup (10cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Large cup or mug (25cl)				<input type="checkbox"/> Bowl (30cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Varies (e.g., a bowl at breakfast, a cup at lunch)						
If you have ticked "Varies", please estimate the number of servings you consumed on a typical day, using the explanations below.				<input type="checkbox"/> 2,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 4,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 5,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 6,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 7 <input type="checkbox"/> 7,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 8 and more						
Correspondence:		A mug (25cl) = 2,5 servings										
Example: 1 bowl of tea in the morning and 1 large cup at lunch = 3 + 2,5 = 5,5 servings per day												
What did you most commonly use when preparing black tea?		<input type="checkbox"/> Tea bags or capsules <input type="checkbox"/> Loose leaf tea				<input type="checkbox"/> Both <input type="checkbox"/> Other / Don't know						
How did you drink your black tea?		<input type="checkbox"/> Light <input type="checkbox"/> Medium				<input type="checkbox"/> Strong <input type="checkbox"/> Other / Don't know						
Select the type(s) of black tea you drank most often		<input type="checkbox"/> Earl Grey <input type="checkbox"/> Darjeeling <input type="checkbox"/> English breakfast				<input type="checkbox"/> Oolong <input type="checkbox"/> Other / Don't know						
	Never	1 to 3 times a month	Once a week	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	Twice a day	3 times a day	4 times a day	5 times a day or more		
Green Tea	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
When you consumed a green tea, what was your typical serving size?		<input type="checkbox"/> Standard cup (10cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Large cup or mug (25cl)				<input type="checkbox"/> Bowl (30cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Varies (e.g., a bowl at breakfast, a cup at lunch)						
If you have ticked "Varies", please estimate the number of servings you consume on a typical day, using the explanations below				<input type="checkbox"/> 2,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 4,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 <input type="checkbox"/> 5,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 6,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 7 <input type="checkbox"/> 7,5 <input type="checkbox"/> 8 and more						
What did you most commonly use when preparing green tea?		<input type="checkbox"/> Tea bags or capsules <input type="checkbox"/> Loose leaf tea				<input type="checkbox"/> Both <input type="checkbox"/> Other / Don't know						
How did you drink your green tea?		<input type="checkbox"/> Light <input type="checkbox"/> Medium				<input type="checkbox"/> Strong <input type="checkbox"/> Other / Don't know						
Did you add mint to your green tea?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes				<input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes			

7.3. During the past year, have you **consumed herbal teas/infusions, including Yerba mate** at least once a month?

- No *(Please proceed directly to question 7.4)*
 Yes *(Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below)*

BEVERAGE	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS								
	1 to 3 times a month	Once a week	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	Twice a day	3 times a day	4 times a day or more	
Herbal tea	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
When you consumed an herbal tea, what was your typical serving size?		<input type="checkbox"/> Standard cup (10cl)			<input type="checkbox"/> Bowl (30cl)				
		<input type="checkbox"/> Large cup or mug (25cl)							
Select 1 to 3 types of ingredients or herbal tea that you most commonly consumed		<input type="checkbox"/> Chamomile <input type="checkbox"/> Hibiscus <input type="checkbox"/> Verbena <input type="checkbox"/> Linden <input type="checkbox"/> Mint <input type="checkbox"/> Red fruits		<input type="checkbox"/> Yerba Mate <input type="checkbox"/> Strawberry/raspberry leaves <input type="checkbox"/> Lemon balm <input type="checkbox"/> Ginseng <input type="checkbox"/> Rooibos <input type="checkbox"/> Thyme <input type="checkbox"/> Other:					

7.4. During the past year, have you consumed hot chocolate at least once a month?

Note: If you consumed hot chocolate once a week during the three winter months, this corresponds to 12 occasions of consumption over the year, equivalent to once a month.

- No *(Please proceed directly to question 8)*
 Yes *(Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below)*

BEVERAGE	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS							
	1 to 3 times a month	Once a week	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	Twice a day	3 times a day	4 times a day or more
Hot chocolate/cocoa	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
When you consumed a hot chocolate, what was your typical serving size?		<input type="checkbox"/> Standard cup (10cl)			<input type="checkbox"/> Bowl (30cl)			
		<input type="checkbox"/> Large cup or mug (25cl)						
When preparing hot chocolate, what did you usually use?		<input type="checkbox"/> 100% cocoa powder (unsweetened) <i>(e.g. Vanhouten, Ghirardelli, or equivalent)</i>		<input type="checkbox"/> Capsule or pod <input type="checkbox"/> Other / Don't know				
		<input type="checkbox"/> Breakfast cocoa powder <i>(e.g. Nesquik, Benco, Poulain, or equivalent)</i>						

8. ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES

Alcoholic beverages are often under-reported by respondents. For the reliability of the results, we kindly ask you to be as honest as possible. The questionnaire is intended for scientific purposes only and will be treated anonymously, without any form of judgment.

8.1. During the past year, have you consumed **wine** at least once a month?

- No (Please proceed directly to question 8.2)
 Yes (Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below)

For each type of wine, please indicate:

On the first line, the number of months per year you consumed this beverage

On the second line, your frequency of consumption during that period

If you never consume a particular beverage, simply tick the "never" box and move on to the next beverage

On the third line, indicate the number of glass(es) you typically drank on each occasion of consumption.

Note: Reference serving size = a glass of wine ~12,5 cl

BEVERAGE	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS												
	Never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 months	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
Red Wine	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Number of glasses of red wine typically consumed per occasion of consumption <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more													
Which type(s) of red wine have you consumed most often? <input type="checkbox"/> Not tannic <input type="checkbox"/> Tannic <input type="checkbox"/> Both <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know													
White wine (including sparkling wine)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Number of glasses of white wine typically consumed per occasion of consumption <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more													
Rose wine (including sparkling wine)	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times per month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
Number of glasses of Rosé wine typically consumed per occasion of consumption <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more													

8.2. During the past year, have you consumed **cider or beer** at least once a month?

- No (*Please proceed directly to question 9*)
 Yes (*Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below*)

For each type of beverage, please indicate:

On the first line, the number of months per year you consumed this beverage

On the second line, your frequency of consumption during that period

If you never consume a particular beverage, simply tick the "never" box and move on to the next beverage

You will also indicate the typical serving size and the number of servings that you usually drank on each occasion of consumption.

Serving sizes:

Half-pint
(25 cl)

Bottle / Can of beer
(33 cl)

Pint
(50 cl)

BEVERAGE	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS												
	Never	1 month	2 months	3 months	4 month	5 months	6 months	7 months	8 months	9 months	10 months	11 months	12 months
Beer	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
When you drank beer, what was your typical serving size?				<input type="checkbox"/> Half-pint (25 cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Can or bottle (33 cl)				<input type="checkbox"/> Pint (50 cl)					
How many servings did you typically drink on each occasion of consumption?					<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2		<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more				
Which type(s) of beer have you consumed most often?				<input type="checkbox"/> Blond (ex. Heineken, 1664) <input type="checkbox"/> Dark or Amber <input type="checkbox"/> Wheat or White beer				<input type="checkbox"/> IPA <input type="checkbox"/> Other / Don't know					
Cider	0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>	11 <input type="checkbox"/>	12 <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Once a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 4 times a month <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to 6 times a week <input type="checkbox"/> Once a day <input type="checkbox"/> 2 to 3 times a day													
When you drank cider, what was your typical serving size?				<input type="checkbox"/> Half-pint (25 cl) <input type="checkbox"/> Can or bottle (33 cl)				<input type="checkbox"/> Pint (50 cl)					
How many servings did you typically drink on each occasion of consumption?					<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2		<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more				

9. CEREAL PRODUCTS

9.1. During the past year, have you consumed **special breads** (excluding white bread, sandwich bread, and toast) at least once a month?

- No (*Please proceed directly to question 9.2*)
- Yes (*Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below*)

Note: Reference portion = 1 slice (approximately 50g)

For each type of speciality bread listed below, please indicate how often you consumed them and the number of slices you typically consumed per occasion.

FOOD	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS						
	Never or <once a month	Once a month	2 to 4 times a month	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	2 to 3 times a day
SPECIAL BREAD							
Whole wheat or wheat bran bread	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Number of slices typically consumed per occasion of consumption</i>		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more	
Whole rye bread	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Number of slices typically consumed per occasion of consumption</i>		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more	
Multigrain bread	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Number of slices typically consumed per occasion of consumption</i>		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more	
Sesame seed bread	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Number of slices typically consumed per occasion of consumption</i>		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more	
Flaxseed bread	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Number of slices typically consumed per occasion of consumption</i>		<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5 or more	

10. COOKING INGREDIENTS (OIL, HERBS, SPICES, AND CONDIMENTS)

10.1. Please describe your typical consumption of **virgin olive oil** and **sesame oil** over the past year, using the following standard portion:

Note : Reference portion for oil = one tablespoon = 15 ml

FOOD (portion)	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS							
	Never or <once a month	Once a month	2 to 4 times a month	2 to 3 times a week	4 to 6 times a week	Once a day	2 to 3 times a day	4 times a day or more
Virgin olive oil (1 tablespoon)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sesame oil (1 tablespoon)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

10.2. Over the past year, have you consumed **spices/herbs** or other condiments (including olives) at least once a month?

- No (*Please proceed directly to question 10.3*)
- Yes (*Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below*)

FOOD (portion)	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS				
	Never	Less than once a month	1 to 3 times a month	1 to 3 times a week	More than 3 times a week
HERBS (1/2 teaspoon dried or 5-8 fresh leaves)					
Parsley	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Thyme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Basil	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rosemary	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mint	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Coriander	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Celeri leaves	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Never	Less than once a month	1 to 3 times a month	1 to 3 times a week	More than 3 times a week
Oregano	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Herbes de Provence	<input type="checkbox"/>				
OTHERS CONDIMENTS					
Capers (2 teaspoons)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Green pesto (1 teaspoon)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Lemon/Lemon juice (as seasoning) (1 lemon slice / 1 teaspoon)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Lime/Lime juice (as seasoning) (1 lemon slice / 1 teaspoon)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Black olives (≈ 8 olives)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Green olives (≈ 8 olives)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
SPICES (1/2 teaspoon dried)					
Cinnamon	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Paprika	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Curcuma	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Chili pepper	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Cumin	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Curry	<input type="checkbox"/>				

10.3. Did you usually consume other spices **more than twice a week**?

- No *(Please go directly to question 11)*
- Yes *(Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below)*

Others spices	Number of serving

12. DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS

Over the past year, have you consumed **plant-based dietary supplements** for at least 15 days?

No

Yes *(Please describe your consumption by filling out the table below)*

	CONSUMPTION OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS		
	Never or less than 15 days per year	Short-term use (15 days to 3 months per year)	Long-term use (from 6 to 12 months)
DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS			
Soy Isoflavones/soy extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Aronia extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Grapeseed extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Green tea extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Citrus extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cranberry /blueberry / Acai / acerola / other berry extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ginseng extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pine bark extract (e.g. Pycnogenol)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wheatgerm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Resveratrol	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Quercetin	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Curcuma	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Red clover extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Green coffee extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
St.John's wort extract	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Flavonoids	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other plant extracts	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>